

Investigation of T-Joint Butt Welding of Plain Carbon Steels With Metal Active Gas Welding in Pb Position

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Received: 15.02.2025

Accepted: 20.03.2025

Abstract

The metal active gas welding (MAG) method is a technique that can be applied to almost all metals suitable for welding. One of the most important features of this method is that the desired welding quality can be achieved with high melting power and high welding speed. The aim of this experimental study is to determine which filler materials are more suitable for welding of PB/T-JOINT BW position by MAG welding method between S235JR quality steels by non-destructive inspection (NDI) methods. The result of this study will contribute to formation of a 'Welding Procedure Specification (WPS) which is used in the company. The WPS is extremely important and it is ensured that another welder can perform the welding process with the same parameters by adhering to the specification independently from the welder.

Keywords: Metal active gas welding, S 235 JR steel, filler materials

1. Introduction

Welding is one of the most fundamental manufacturing processes used in various industries, including construction, automotive, aerospace, and shipbuilding. Among different welding techniques, Metal Active Gas (MAG) welding is widely applied due to its high efficiency, ease of automation, and ability to produce high-quality welds with minimal defects (Yılmaz and Barlas, 2004). Empirical studies on the basis of the microstructural and mechanical characteristics have demonstrated that gas metal arc welding results in finer grain structures and enhanced mechanical properties compared to other conventional welding methods (Muzafferoğlu, 2008; Sekban and Kılıçaslan, 2023). Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) is a widely adopted welding technique in industrial applications, where shielding gases are utilized to protect the welding zone from adverse atmospheric conditions (Anonymous, 2023). GMAW processes are categorized into non-consumable (Tungsten Inert Gas, TIG) and consumable electrode methods (Metal Inert Gas, MIG and Metal Active Gas, MAG) welding, depending on the type of electrode used (Anık and Vural, 1996). S235JR, a non-alloyed low-carbon structural steel, is frequently preferred in steel construction, shipbuilding, and machinery manufacturing due to its good weldability and sufficient mechanical properties. S235JR is a non-alloy structural steel defined by the EN 10025 standard, with a yield strength of approximately 235 MPa. Due to its low carbon content (typically around 0.17% C) and the presence of manganese, it exhibits high weldability. With the appropriate filler material and welding parameters, strong weld seams can be achieved without crack formation. (Rogalski et al., 2014, Kaya, 2018). Additionally, the GMAW method is widely applied in the joining of aluminum alloys by the selection of appropriate welding parameters significantly influences weld quality (Merican et al., 2020). welding speed is the most critical parameter for achieving the desired fillet weld leg length in practical applications. The authors emphasized that by selecting appropriate welding parameters, an

optimal weld profile can be obtained in low-carbon steels, preventing both excessively large and heavy welds as well as weak and undersized welds (Ghazvinloo, 2024). Also, the study found that as the welding speed decreases, heat input increases, resulting in a wider and fuller weld leg, whereas an increase in speed leads to a narrower weld seam in the welding of S235JR steel. In MAG welding, variations in parameters such as current, voltage, wire feed speed, and shielding gas composition can significantly affect the strength and toughness of welded joints in steels like S235JR (Sabev et al., 2024). In the context of weld defect detection and quality enhancement, advanced methodologies have been explored. Non-destructive inspection (NDI) techniques will be utilized to evaluate weld integrity, and the results will contribute to the development of a Welding Procedure Specification (WPS) that can standardize the welding process within industrial applications. Therefore, the aim of this experimental study is to determine the most suitable filler materials for welding S235JR steel in the PB/T-JOINT BW position using the MAG welding method through non-destructive inspection (NDI) techniques. The results of this study will contribute to the development of the Welding Procedure Specification (WPS) used in the company. The WPS is of critical importance, as it ensures that another welder can perform the welding process independently while adhering to the specified parameters.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Sample preparation

The chemical composition of S235JR quality steel and used filler materials (welding rods) are given in Table 1. The casting numbers (heat no) of S235JR steels were verified by checking their certificates and then were cut in the dimensions of 8x150x250 (plate 1) and 6x150x250 mm (plate 2) by CNC plasma cutting machine. The cut plates were joined by gas metal arc welding in PB/T-JOINT BW position with the filler material given in Table 1 Afterwards, the necessary cleanings were made and subjected to destructive and non-

destructive inspection procedures. A 'V' shaped welding mouth was opened with a 30° welding mouth angle and a 2 mm gap (Figure 1a) for the plates that will come to the 1st plate position in Figure 1b. The rail oxy cutting machine was used in the welding mouth preparation process. The surface cleaning was done appropriately. While cleaning the surface, firstly burrs and impregnations were cleaned with a bowl brush and a stone motor suitable for the material. Figure 1b shows the PB/T-

JOINT BW which is an abbreviation used in welding terminology. PB: As a position code, PB (2F) refers to a horizontal fillet weld. T-JOINT: Indicates a welding joint where two materials are joined in a T-shape (at a 90° angle). BW (Butt Weld): Refers to a welding process in which the workpieces are joined edge to edge by aligning their surfaces directly against each other. This phrase most likely means "a butt weld in a T-joint connection in the PB position."

Table 1. The chemical composition of S235 JR quality steel and filler materials¹

	% C	% Mn	% P	% S	% Si	% Cr	% Ni	% Fe
S235JR (6 mm)	0.155	0.402	0.005	0.014	0.020	0.012	0.009	balance
S235JR (8 mm)	0.060	0.520	0.012	0.007	0.030	0.070	0.090	balance
SG 2 (Ø 1mm)	0.065	1.55	0.006	0.005	0.89	0.02	0.03	balance
309 L Si (Ø 1mm)	0.03	1.8	-	-	0.8	23.5	13.0	balance
316 L Si (Ø 1mm)	0.01	1.58	0.004	0.019	0.86	18.22	11.1	balance

¹The chemical composition ratios were obtained from the certificates of the respective materials used.

Figure 1. a) A 'V' shaped welding mouth, b) PB/T-joint BW position (TS EN ISO 6947:2019), c) small pieces

In order to prevent the welding start and end points, where welding errors are more common, from affecting our experiment; after the welding process small pieces that need to be removed were added to these areas using the spot welding method (Figure 1c). In order to minimize the deformations called distortions that will occur during welding as a result of the heat input to the material, small pieces are fixed behind the plates also.

2.2. Welding process

In PB position, the work pieces must be positioned in a horizontal/vertical corner

position. The torch tip should be held at a 45-degree angle during the welding process. By the way verification was made for the welding machine before starting the welding process. Figure 2a shows the welding process and the produced samples are shown in Figure 2b. The plates placed at the welding start and end points where welding errors are more common were cut and discarded. Then, the sample plates were cleaned of welding spatter and other contamination that occurred during welding. Again, a cup brush and flex were used here.

Figure 2. a) Welding process, b) Produced samples

Table 2. Applied welding parameters for different filler materials

Filler Materials	Weld Layers	Polarity	Current (A)	Voltage (V)	Speed	Travel (cm min ⁻¹)	Heat Input kJ mm ⁻¹ (max)	Inter pass (°C)
SG 2	1st	DC(+)	180-190	24-25		2.27	142.731	250
	2nd	DC(+)	215	26-27		1.61	264.91	250
309 L Si	1st	DC(+)	200-215	24.5-25.5		2.31	79.31	250
	2nd	DC(+)	210-220	25.5-26.5		0.3846	158.31	250
316 L Si	1st	DC(+)	200-215	24.5-25.5		2.31	79.31	250
	2nd	DC(+)	210-220	25.5-26.5		0.3846	158.31	250

Table 2 shows the applied welding parameters for different filler materials. In this study, the surface of the welding metal was preheated to approximately 250 °C before welding. This process was repeated between the passes. The primary purpose of preheating is to minimize the temperature difference between the base metal and the heat generated during welding. If preheating is not done, a temperature difference may occur. This situation increases problems related to distortion and excessive stress. To reduce issues such as warping, cracking, and discontinuities in the weld, the base metal was subjected to preheating.

2.3. Testing procedures

After the welding process was completed, the welds were inspected using destructive and non-destructive testing methods in order to determine welding defects. These methods are as follows.

- Visual inspection according to TS EN ISO 17637 and TS EN ISO 5817 standards
- Macroscopic inspection of welds according to TS EN ISO 17639 standard

- Liquid penetrant inspection according to TS EN ISO 5817, TS EN ISO 3452-1 and TS EN ISO 23277
- Radiographic inspection according to TS EN ISO 17636-1 and TS EN ISO 10675-1 standards
- Ultrasonic inspection according to TS EN ISO 11666 and TS EN ISO 22825 standards
- Hardness test according to TS EN ISO 9015 standard

3. Results and Discussion

The tests performed on the samples and their results are explained below.

3.1 Visual inspection

The plates were checked and discussed with the operator with a level 2 certificate according to the control conditions specified in the TS EN ISO 17637 standard and the class B level of the TS EN ISO 5817 standard. The weld height was measured and no defects such as pores, cracks, or burning grooves were observed.

3.2 Macro Inspection

The surface was polished using 1000-grit sandpaper. The etching process was performed using the immersion technique with a nital etching solution. Inspection were obtained at 3X magnification. The acquired images are presented in the figures below, labeled with the corresponding specimen numbers. Figure 3 shows some results of the macro inspection. There is no any welding defect in the weld pool in Figure 3a. However, Figure 3b shows the defect which is the concavity at the weld root. During welding, the heat input applied to the metal is determined by specific parameters. The heat input is influenced by the travel speed

of the welding torch, the welding metal, and the amperage and voltage values applied during the process. Therefore, these parameters directly affect the amount of heat input. It can be said that the heat input directly influences the welding quality, full penetration, and distortions such as warping in the base metal. Considering the heat inputs applied to the material in Table 2. Another defect is the fusion deficiency which is shown in Figure 3c. It is due to lack of heat input. Therefore, the specimens welded with 309 L Si and 316 L Si did not produce satisfactory results. Similar results were obtained as like radiographic inspection.

Figure 3. Some results of macro inspection; a) SG2; no welding defects, b) 309 L Si; concavity at the weld root, c) 316 L Si; fusion deficiency at the weld root

3.3 Liquid Penetrate Test

There are two types of penetrant testing process, fluorescent and visible. Each method includes some differences including water washable, post-emulsifiable-lipophilic, solvent cleaned and post-emulsifiable-extremely hydrophilic methods. Visible liquid penetrant

testing was applied in this study. Liquid penetrant testing was performed by a level 2 operator in accordance with the standards mentioned above. First, cleaning was done with a solvent-based cleaner in order to clean any dirt, rust, oil, etc. that may cover surface defects. After the cleaning process, penetrant

liquid was applied to the weld surface by spraying (Figure 4a). It was kept like this for 20-25 minutes. After the waiting period was over, the penetrant liquid was cleaned with the cleaner using a lint-free cloth. As the last process, the developer was applied (Figure 4b)

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Liquid penetration test; a) application liquid penetrate, b) application of developer

3.4 Radiographic inspection

Radiographic inspection procedures were performed according to TS EN ISO 17636-1 and TS EN ISO 10675-1 standards and discussed with level 3 operator. A film with dimensions of 240x100 mm was used. Before filming, lead plates were marked and a 10 FE EN penetrometer was used. This film was exposed for 240 seconds with a device with 25 Ci activity at a 45° angle from a distance of 400 mm. The used X-ray is Ir192. After the 240-second exposure time was completed. The film was kept in a dark room under red light for 4 minutes in the developer and then rinsed. After keeping it in the fixer for 4 minutes, the film

was taken to dry. Then, film images are given below along with sample part numbers. Figure 5 shows some results of the radiographic inspection. There is no any welding defect in the weld pool in Figure 5a. The specimen welded with SG 2 yielded a positive result. However, Figure 5b shows the defect which is the concavity at the weld root. It is attributed that the residual stress due to excess heat input creates plastic deformation at the weld root. Another defect is the fusion deficiency which is shown in Figure 5c. It is due to lack of heat input. Therefore, the specimens welded with 309 L Si and 316 L Si did not produce satisfactory results. Similar results were obtained as like macro inspection.

(a)

Figure 5. Some results of radiographic inspection; a) no welding defects, b) concavity at the weld root, c) fusion deficiency at the weld root

3.5 Ultrasonic Inspection

Testing was conducted in accordance with TS EN ISO 11666 and TS EN ISO 22825 standards. The examination was performed on Plate 1, positioned perpendicular to the plate 2 (T-shape). For the S235 JR specimens, a single-crystal angled probe was used instead of dual-crystal angled probe due to grain size in the microstructure. The coarse grain structure increases the probe's dead zone, making it necessary to use a dual-crystal angled probe to obtain the most accurate results for instance stainless steel specimens. Before commencing the examination, a two-step calibration process

was carried out, consisting of distance calibration and sensitivity calibration. Following calibration, the ultrasonic inspection began. In accordance with the relevant standards, the surface was pre-cleaned to ensure that the distance between the probe and the material surface was less than 0.5 mm. A glycerin gel was applied to the cleaned surface, and the single crystal angled probe was moved perpendicularly to detect vertical defects. To identify transverse defects, the probe was tilted at a 45° angle and moved laterally. The X, Y, and Z axes are provided in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Coordinates of Ultrasonic inspection and X-axis is the welding direction

The inspection process has been completed, and the results are presented below. Although the ultrasonic testing conducted on Samples 1 and 2 yielded positive results, a discontinuity was detected on Sample 3 within the 180-250 mm range along the X-axis, -2 mm on the Y-axis, and 5-8 mm on the Z-axis. Therefore, the ultrasonic test for Sample 3 was not considered successful. Based on the regions specified in the ultrasonic test results, this discontinuity is considered to be located between the 1st and 2nd passes. If we interpret the possible causes based on our technical experience, after the 1st pass, grinding is performed for cleaning. If this cleaning is not done properly, a positive result may not be obtained in non-destructive testing.

Another possibility is that an interpass crack may have formed either during or after the welding of the 2nd pass.

3.6 Hardness test

The Vickers hardness test were conducted in an environment with a temperature of 23 °C and a relative humidity of 0.45. The surfaces of the test specimens were polished using 800-grit paper. Each specimen was measured at 15 different points. These measurement points were designated as the weld region, the heat-affected zone (HAZ), and the base metal, as shown in Figure 7a, 7b.

Figure 7. a) Designation of Position Numbers, b) Variation of Vickers hardness values with position

As shown in Figure 7, the hardness values in the heat-affected zone (HAZ) are generally higher than those in the weld metal and base metal. Therefore, in the event of severance, fractures are expected to occur in these regions. The hardness values measured at points 1, 2, and 3 are approximately equal for all three welding consumables. However, when examining the hardness measurement results at points 13, 14, and 15, while 309 L Si and 316 L Si exhibit similar hardness values, the specimen welded with SG 2 welding wire shows lower hardness values at these points compared to the others. Additionally, in the

specimen welded with 309 L Si welding metal, a sudden increase in hardness is observed at the transition from the weld region to the HAZ. This is generally considered an undesirable condition. The hardness values in the base metal were expected to be similar on both sides, specifically at points 1, 2, 3 and 13, 14, 15. However, considering that the two plates used in this study have different thicknesses, and as indicated in the material certificates, these different thicknesses exhibit variations in tensile strength, yield strength, and elongation values, the differences in hardness results are not unexpected. Similar result was found in the

literature. In welded S235JR joints, the hardness distribution typically follows a gradient, with the highest hardness observed in the weld metal, intermediate hardness in the heat-affected zone (HAZ), and the lowest hardness in the base material. This phenomenon is attributed to the alloying element content and rapid solidification-induced hardening in the weld metal, while partial hardening in the HAZ is associated with the annealing effect. Notably, in a comprehensive thesis study by Gültöplüyan (2025) on the MAG welding of S235 and S355 structural steels, it was reported that in all welding combinations, the highest microhardness values were measured in the weld metal, followed by the HAZ and the base material. In the same study, tensile tests revealed that all specimens fractured on the base material side, indicating that the strength of the weld seams was higher than that of the S235JR itself (Sekban et al., 2023). Alloying elements in metals affect many of the

material's properties. For example, elements like C, Mn, Mo, Cr, V, Nb, and Si are important elements that increase hardness by forming solid solutions. Depending on the cooling rate, the formation of martensite and the likelihood of cracking are controlled by the carbon equivalent value of steel. It is desirable to keep the carbon equivalent as low as possible. Metals with a low carbon equivalent have a higher weldability. Therefore, preheating in metals with a high carbon equivalent can help prevent many issues. C element increases surface hardness of the base metal and other alloying elements increases the hardenability of steel. All of these elements increases the hardness values by formation of solid solution as well as strength values of steel. All conducted tests are briefly summarized in Table 3 below. This table also shows that the confidence and reliability of non-destructive inspection (NDI) method is not reasonable and should be investigated.

Table 3. Total inspection results

Sample Number	Filler Material	1st Plate	2nd Plate	Inspection Methods ⁴				
				VT	MT	PT	RT	UT
1	SG 2	S 235 JR (8 mm)	S 235 JR (6mm)	OK	OK	OK	OK	OK
2	309 L Si	S 235 JR (8 mm)	S 235 JR (6mm)	OK	Rejection	OK	Rejection	OK
3	316 L Si	S 235 JR (8 mm)	S 235 JR (6mm)	OK	Rejection	OK	Rejection	Rejection

⁴VT: Visual Test, MT: Macro Test, PT: Penetration Test, RT: Radiographic Test, UT: Ultrasonic Testing

4. Conclusion

It was observed that the S 235 JR material, when welded to another S 235 JR material, successfully passed all tests, confirming that the most suitable welding wire is SG 2. Specimens welded with other wires did not yield favorable results, as clearly demonstrated in the findings.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved

the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to those who have supported me throughout this study especially to managers and workmate of Erensan Isı Tekniği San. Tic. A.Ş., where I conducted my research.

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To Cite: Yaranoglu, B., Temel, Y., 2025. Current Situation, Problems and Solution Suggestions of Broiler Breeding in Balıkesir Province. *MAS Journal of Applied Sciences*, 10(2): 249–258.
DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15646218>.
